

LOWERING THE ENERGY AND WATER FOOTPRINT OF A LAUNDRY FACILITY

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Abstract

Rapidly increasing prices of fuels, electricity and, subsequently, of all utilities, force industrial enterprises to reduce their energy footprint. Following this need, small and medium enterprises face additional barriers compared to large industries. Shorter annual working time and unfavourable economy of scale typically allow for simple low-cost solutions to be implemented only. This indicates that an untapped potential for becoming more energy efficient still exists in small and medium enterprises. A case study performed in an industrial laundry company aimed at identifying economically feasible energy saving measures confirmed this assumption. A discrepancy between actual and benchmarked water and energy consumption in the washing process was revealed with the help of dedicated on-site measurements. Further analyses will follow, focused on the drying process as well as on the steam production efficiency.

Introduction

Energy efficiency and sustainable operation of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) belongs to key pillars of reducing industrial energy consumption and related greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions^{1,2}. Compared to large industrial entities, SMEs face additional challenges in following this goal^{3,4}. Firstly, their annual working time is usually shorter, and several operations are performed batch-wise, on the contrary to continuous production processes in most large industries. As a result, simple and easily implemented projects constitute the majority of the actions undertaken to reduce energy consumption, waste creation and GHG emissions^{5,6}. Secondly, various technical, economic and other barriers⁷⁻⁹ must be usually overcome in SMEs to implement, monitor and target any such energy saving-related measure.

Internal or external benchmarking programmes¹⁰ and energy audits^{11,12} represent well-known and reliable tools in facilitating the needed changes in energy management of any energy consumer. Experiences from various countries¹³⁻¹⁵ confirm that energy consumption and the related expenses can be cut down by several percent just by screening for standard measures and their adoption. These include but are not limited to: improving the utilities consumption recording systems, implementing more efficient equipment, paying more attention to preventive maintenance, utilizing renewable energy sources, upgrading process control, and facilitating changes in habits of energy consumers¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Besides cutting down the operational expenses, further benefits of making the production more sustainable include environmental load reduction^{19,20}, new jobs opportunities and increased market competitiveness^{21,22}.

Laundry services are characteristic by high energy and water consumption associated with textiles' washing and drying²³. Recommended actions to be undertaken in such industrial branch comprise partial water reuse²⁴, heat recovery^{25,26}, heat source operation optimization, and water heating by solar energy²⁷. Additional savings can result from optimized operation management²⁸.

Lindström is a small enterprise in the laundry industry, focused on renting and laundry of industrial workwear and floor mats²⁹. The goal of our study was the assessment of energies and media utilization, and the analysis of media consumption trends. The results were used to propose energy efficiency measures.

Materials and methods

The enterprise operates eight laundry washing modules divided into two sections. The first section is specialized in washing workwear (WW), the other in washing mats. Each module contains two large capacity washing machines and a large capacity drying machine, with modules in the WW section additionally containing one smaller washing and drying machine. The module WW1 is powered entirely by electricity as well as all the aforementioned smaller devices in the entire WW section. Electricity also powers all the motors, displays, lights and some regulation elements in all of the modules. In the remaining modules the main energy demand, which is used for heating of process water or air, is supplied by steam. This steam is generated in two ways. In modules WW2, MAT1 and MAT2 the steam is generated in a compact steam boiler, which is incorporated into the

structure of the module itself. In the case of modules WW3, WW4, MAT3 and MAT4, the steam is generated in the nearby boiler room. The layout of the enterprise is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2. Layout of the enterprise

A measurement of the washing and drying programs was carried out at the enterprise in order to obtain the amount of steam used in these programs at the module MAT4. The washing program is divided into two washes, with the first one using recycled water from the last program, which is discarded after the wash. The second wash uses chemically treated water (CHTW). After the second wash it is lead through a filter into the recycled water reservoir, where it is stored for the next washing program. The piping of the machines as well as related devices was adjusted for the measurement, as shown in Figure 2. The amount of moisture present in mats was determined by differential mass measurement. The mats were weighed before and after the washing program, and the amount of moisture was determined as the difference of these two values. This information was then also used in the calculation of the drying program. The amount of drain water in both of the washes was determined volumetrically. The drain water was collected in 200 l cylindrical barrels; the water level was measured in each of the barrels and the volume of water in each barrel was calculated. Then, assuming the density of this water to be that of pure water at the same temperature, the mass of drain water was determined.

Figure 3. Flow diagram of the measurement of the washing and drying programs (adjustments and measurements shown in grey).

The results of the measurement were processed using a mass and enthalpy balance equation system to show theoretical and real steam and water consumption values. Further details of the calculation can be found in³⁰.

The theoretical steam consumption of the drying machine was determined using its nominal power output. Real drying air consumption was determined by numerical integration of the flow profile data using equation (1),

$$\dot{V} = \frac{\pi}{4} \int_0^r v_r r dr \quad (1)$$

where \dot{V} is the volumetric flow of air, r is the distance of the point of measurement from the axis of the pipe and v_r is the velocity of the air at the point of measurement.

Real steam consumption was then determined using the enthalpy balance of the heat exchanger in the drying machine.

Consumption data, which was provided by the enterprise, was processed to show a relationship between media consumption and production volume by combining data relevant to the studied device, groups of devices with the same powering method or entire WW or MAT sections into graphs. These were then assessed to identify energy efficiency shortcomings. The assumption was that batch processes would provide linear relationships with minimal scatter or intercept value due to the fact that batch production is the iteration of the same process, therefore consumption should be solely a function of processed batches. Any deviation from this state would signify energy inefficiency. For example, an increased intercept value (increased constant consumption) could indicate a leak from an inaccessible piping, which could be otherwise impossible to identify. Further information on the methods of analysis of consumption data relationships can be found in³¹.

Results

The measurement of the washing program yielded results shown in Table I.

Table I
Measurement of the washing program results

	1 st measurement		2 nd measurement		3 rd measurement
$m_{\text{mats;dirty}}$ [kg]	80.9	$m_{\text{mats;dirty}}$ [kg]	76.8	$m_{\text{mats;dirty}}$ [kg]	81.4
$m_{\text{mats;wet}}$ [kg]	96.1	$m_{\text{mats;wet}}$ [kg]	94.2	$m_{\text{mats;wet}}$ [kg]	91.8
m_{moisture} [kg]	15.2	m_{moisture} [kg]	17.4	m_{moisture} [kg]	10.4
$m_{\text{drain;1st wash}}$ [kg]	258.5	$m_{\text{drain;1st wash}}$ [kg]	220.6	$m_{\text{drain;1st wash}}$ [kg]	227.8
$m_{\text{drain;2nd wash}}$ [kg]	343.0	$m_{\text{drain;2nd wash}}$ [kg]	323.8	$m_{\text{drain;2nd wash}}$ [kg]	286.7
m_{drain} [kg]	601.5	m_{drain} [kg]	544.4	m_{drain} [kg]	514.5

The air flow velocity profile measured in the drying machine is visualized in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Visualization of the flow profile in the drying machine outlet pipe.

The outputs of calculations of the washing and drying programs are shown in Tables II-IV.

Table II
Results of the calculation of the washing program

Measurement [kg/batch]	Theoretical	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	Average
m _{RW}	158	267.1	229.9	232.1	243.0
m _{CHTW}	182	322.0	303.9	269.1	298.3
m _{steam}	15.3	27.4	25.5	23.4	25.4

Table III
Results of the calculation of the drying program

m _{steam; theoretical} [kg/batch]	27
m _{steam} [kg/batch]	26.1

Table IV
Comparison of the results with monthly production data

Lindström washing machine data	Average CHTW per batch [kg]		
Batches per year	19 664	Lindström data	314.4
Water per year [m ³]	6 182	Measurement	298.3

The graphs, which were used to identify an energy inefficiency and propose a mitigating measure are shown in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 5. Water consumption relationship.

Figure 6. Gas consumption relationship.

Discussion

The direct results of the measurements, shown in Table I and Figure 3 were first processed using the described calculation methods. At first, in the measurement of the washing program, only steam consumption was desired, however, a considerable discrepancy between theoretical and real amount of used water in the washing program was discovered based on data in Table II. The presence of this discrepancy was further confirmed by comparison of output data with monthly production data provided by the enterprise, as shown in Table IV. Upon further examination of the machines and consultation with the enterprise, we identified, that upon rotation of the drum, the textile mats absorb some of the washing water, reducing the water level in the machine, which prompts the inlet pump to add more water into the mix. The amount of additional water corresponds with the amount of water that the mats can hold, which further confirms this effect. We recommended that the enterprise consult this discrepancy with the company responsible for washing program management in order to change the settings of the inlet pump, so that only the amount of water described in the washing program definition is pumped. Potential annual savings of 12% of total water and gas expenditure of the enterprise were anticipated upon mitigating this inefficiency on all relevant modules. The enterprise has implemented this measure on modules MAT3 and MAT4, and is already reporting savings of 5 m³ of water per day.

No discrepancy was found with the measurement and calculation of the drying program, as can be seen in Table III, and the resulting values were considered correct, therefore, they were used for further energy assessment at the enterprise.

The consumption and production trends, which can be observed in Figures 4 and 5, indicate that the relationship in the MAT section displays expected qualities with minimal scatter, as shown by the R² value and proportionally low intercept value. However, we can also observe, that the relationships in the WW section display greater scatter from a linear relationship as well as proportionally greater intercept. Based on this information and upon consultation with the enterprise, we identified a possible cause. Metal and plastic bits (bolts, coins, screws, pens, screwdrivers), are often forgotten in the rented WW by the customers of the enterprise. These then fall out of the WW during the washing program and jam the outlet valve. This leads to high water and energy losses due to pumping of heated water into the machine, which then immediately goes down the drain. This continues until the operator of the machine notices that the first step of the wash is taking too long. At first, installation of a filter with magnetic separator was proposed to mitigate this inefficiency, this was however deemed impossible to implement by the staff of the enterprise due to the geometry of the washing machine. The bits fall into the valve through a gap between the drum and the door of the washing machine. Therefore, installation of a rubber or nylon brush “gasket” at this spot, which would allow the rotation of the drum and allow water to pass through, but would stop any larger pieces of material, was proposed.

Conclusions

A case study confirmed that SMEs indeed exhibit unutilized energy efficiency potential. Due to this fact, energy auditing can often lead to the proposal of low investment, short payback time measures; therefore, it is cost effective for SMEs to be subjected to such auditing³². Mitigation measures were proposed, which would increase energy efficiency at the enterprise. The implementation of one of the mitigation measures led to significant water and subsequently energy savings.

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References

1. Malinauskaitė J., Jouhara H., Ahmad. L., Milani M., Montorsi L., Venturelli M.: *Energy* 172, 255 (2019).
2. Rehfeldt M., Worrell E., Eichhammer W., Fleiter T.: *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev.* 120, 109672 (2020).
3. Cagno E., Neri A., Trianni A.: *Energy Effic.* 11, 1193 (2018).
4. Fleiter T., Worrell E., Eichhammer W.: *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev.* 15, 3099 (2011).
5. Hrovatin N., Cagno E., Dolšák J., Zorić J.: *J. Cleaner Prod.* 323, 129123 (2021).
6. Máša V., Stehlík P., Touš M., Vondra M.: *Energy* 158, 293 (2018).
7. Palm J., Backman F.: *Energy Effic.* 13, 809 (2020).
8. Therkelsen P., McKane A.: *Energy Policy* 57, 318 (2013).

9. Mahapatra K., Alm R., Hallgren R., Bischoff L., Tuglu N., Kuai L., Yang Y., Umoru I.: *Energy Effic.* *11*, 1103 (2018).
10. Locmelis K., Blumberga D., Blumberga A., Kubule A.: *Energies* *13*, 2210 (2020).
11. Kalantzis F., Revoltella D.: *Energy Econ.* *83*, 229 (2019).
12. Fresner J., Morea F., Krenn Ch., Aranda Uson J., Tomasi F.: *J. Cleaner Prod.* *142*, 1650 (2017).
13. Patel J. D., Shah R., Trivedi R. H.: *J. Cleaner Prod.* *333*, 130170 (2022).
14. Redmond J., Walker B.: *Energy Effic.* *9*, 1053 (2015).
15. Cunha P., Neves S. A., Marques A. C., Serrasqueiro Z.: *Energy Policy* *146*, 111776 (2020).
16. Errigo A., Choi J.-K., Kissock K.: *Sustainable Energy Tech. Assess.* *49*, 101694 (2022).
17. Andersson E., Karlsson M., Thollander P., Paramonova S.: *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev.* *93*, 165 (2018).
18. Birat J.-P., Declich A., Quinti G., Signore P., Fick G., Chiappini M., Millet D., Alix T.: *Mater. Tech.* *108*, 505 (2021).
19. Fadly, D.: *Sustainability* *12*, 7455 (2020).
20. Viesi D., Pozzar F., Federici A., Crema L., Mahbub M. S.: *Energy Policy* *105*, 363 (2017).
21. Maciková L., Smorada M., Dorčák P., Beug B., Markovič P.: *Sustainability* *10*, 2274 (2018).
22. Malega P., Majerník M., Rudy V., Daneshjo N.: *Pol. J. Environ. Stud.* *30*, 3753 (2021).
23. Bobák P., Pavlas M., Kšenzuliak V., Stehlík P.: *Chem. Eng. Trans.* *21*, 109 (2010).
24. Nicolaidis Ch., Vyrides I.: *Resour., Conserv. Recycl.* *92*, 128 (2014).
25. Conde M. R.: *Appl. Therm. Eng.* *17*, 1163 (1997).
26. Valenti G., Bonacina C. N., Bamoshmoosh A.: *Case Stud. Therm. Eng.* *22*, 100734 (2020).
27. Lima T. P., Dutra J. C. C., Primo A. R. M., Rohatgi J., Ochoa A. A. V.: *Sol. Energy* *122*, 737 (2015).
28. Nunes J. R. R., da Silva J. E. A. R., da Silva Moris V. A., Giannetti B. F.: *J. Cleaner Prod.* *218*, 357 (2019).
29. <https://lindstromgroup.com/>
30. Čižmár M., Variny M., Vráblik P.: *Proceedings of the 16th Biannual CER Comparative European Research Conference*, 114 (2021).
31. Hasanbeigi A., Price L.: *Ernest Orlando Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory* (2010).
32. Thollander P., Kimura O., Wakabayashi M., Rohdin P.: *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev.* *50*, 504 (2015).